

Workflow of time course image quantification – by Florian Pruckner

Image acquisitions:

Generally all images (in one experiment) were acquired with the same acquisition parameters. In case I had oversaturation of fluorescence in a picture, I lowered the laser intensity of both lasers (red and green) to the same extend. Usually that was to 50%, but this was only on rare occasions.

Usage of the FIJI macro:

1. Drag it into FIJI
2. Chose the right channels that will be analyzed. This depends on what the channels were in taking the acquisitions with ZEN. In my case: Ch1 was red, Ch2 transmitted light and Ch3 green. So I set it accordingly as in the picture.

3. Drag the picture you want to analyze into FIJI and just press OK for the default settings.
4. Set line width to whatever you please (double click). I chose for all experiments line width = 100

It changes the area over that the fluorescence will be integrated.

5. Press "Run" in the macro

6. Draw the line you want to analyze over the picture with the mouse

7. Press "OK" at the "Draw line on projection."-Window.

8. The macro runs and automatically opens a graph with the intensity curves. You can close it.

The excel files with the fluorescence intensities are stored automatically for each channel separately at the location of your original ZEN image.

9. I copied all the fluorescence intensities from one experiment into a single excel file that is used for further analysis. It can be found in the folder of the corresponding experiment. In the different sheets you find the data for each timepoint and genotype

10. In red columns from 1-12 it is the fluorescence of the virus in the corresponding meristem, in green columns the fluorescence of the CLV3::H2B-Clover.

On the left side is the raw data summarized

On the right side is the data normalized

The screenshot shows an Excel spreadsheet with two main sections of data. The left section, labeled 'BN64', contains raw data with columns 1-12 in red and columns 13-24 in green. The right section contains normalized data with columns 25-36 in red and columns 37-48 in green. Blue arrows point from the text above to the respective sections of the spreadsheet. The spreadsheet contains multiple rows of numerical data, with some cells highlighted in yellow.

How I normalized:

As intensities vary from meristem to meristem, depending how deep it is embedded, or if it is covered by a pedal, I tried to bring all CLV3 green fluorescence's to the same level. I adjusted all curves so that the maximum value would be 100.

$$\text{normalized curve} = \text{notnormalized curve} * \frac{100}{\text{max.value(of the curve)}}$$

In excel it would look for example like this:

=IF(P2="", "", P2*100/MAX(P\$2:P\$373))

(I used a "IF" function to not have division by 0 problems in case a column is empty.. so: IF("if P2 is empty; then leave field empty; else use this formula"))

The red fluorescence was adjusted by the same factor that the green fluorescence was.

11. Further on the right in the excel sheets I calculated the average intensities in the meristems.

For green fluorescence all non-Mock meristems were averaged.

=AVERAGE(AQ2:BB2)

For red all non-Mock meristems were averaged and the mock red intensity (Autofluorescence) was subtracted.

=AVERAGE(AD2:AO2)-AC2

	EO	EP	BQ	BR	BS
	5.01155591	13.16276595	3.07334538	5.5882	8.0846
	4.550295243	14.6787283	3.53072375	1.0185	8.081
	5.2594426	16.4005918	4.02623434	1.9059	5.2292
	5.20370246	18.6541121	4.86293941	1.9405	11.066
	7.42088205	21.20493018	5.67862427	1.5332	13.231
	9.949395448	24.5000039	7.94682022	1.7053	16.115
	10.6387802	28.83875191	8.71897053	1.92	19.344
	12.58767863	33.8853931	10.39670171	2.181	22.864
	14.85072742	39.1103881	12.2342771	2.385	26.785
	16.34872443	44.75950474	14.0513883	2.2973	30.4
	18.11861712	50.2973402	15.57625591	2.5411	33.686
	19.5134398	56.14745305	16.82044551	2.6823	36.334
	20.52230668	62.2332381	17.87233487	2.85	38.986
	21.43727852	68.37627975	18.42083952	3.0863	41.659
	22.1257185	74.24850224	18.65778393	3.4747	40.79
	22.66867115	79.8302524	18.7881919	3.0793	41.475
	23.17256898	84.33831754	18.87886891	4.2989	42.045
	23.6748803	87.9487644	18.5084006	4.7552	42.074
	24.16862638	90.3320878	18.8888884	5.0667	43.065
	24.37032206	92.3043503	18.2290728	5.1604	43.6
	24.47927117	93.52787676	18.40702546	4.7422	44.286
	25.1988179	93.86503008	18.46627932	5.7313	44.662
	25.3789888	93.8558604	18.3086731	6.0073	44.627
	25.47183804	91.44380151	18.27887875	6.1413	44.683
	25.6050940	88.38237591	18.3702916	6.2807	45.021
	26.8829786	66.8436271	18.8623188	6.2234	45.346
	28.68442638	62.14587198	20.4553415	6.2238	47.14
	27.05227978	78.084148	21.0580238	5.5384	48.071
	27.28242768	74.18847253	21.41781256	5.8444	48.68
	27.1987828	70.02742818	21.95821916	6.1091	48.437

12. I calculated the standard deviation for the set of red fluorescence intensities.

Standard deviation

Lower band
(mScarlet mean-Stan.Dev)

Upper band
(mScarlet mean+Stan.Dev)

	EO	EP	BQ	BR	BS
	5.01155591	13.16276595	3.07334538	5.5882	8.0846
	4.550295243	14.6787283	3.53072375	1.0185	8.081
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	10.6387802	28.83875191	8.71897053	1.92	19.344
	12.58767863	33.8853931	10.39670171	2.181	22.864
	14.85072742	39.1103881	12.2342771	2.385	26.785
	16.34872443	44.75950474	14.0513883	2.2973	30.4
	18.11861712	50.2973402	15.57625591	2.5411	33.686
	19.5134398	56.14745305	16.82044551	2.6823	36.334
	20.52230668	62.2332381	17.87233487	2.85	38.986
	21.43727852	68.37627975	18.42083952	3.0863	41.659
	22.1257185	74.24850224	18.65778393	3.4747	40.79
	22.66867115	79.8302524	18.7881919	4.2989	42.045
	23.17256898	84.33831754	18.87886891	4.2993	42.045
	23.6748803	87.9487644	18.5084006	4.7552	42.814
	24.16862638	90.3320878	18.8888884	5.0667	43.065
	24.37032206	92.3043503	18.2290728	5.1604	43.6
	24.47927117	93.52787676	18.40702546	4.7422	44.286
	25.1988179	93.86503008	18.46627932	5.7313	44.662
	25.3789888	93.8558604	18.3086731	6.0073	44.627
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